

DOME webinar

Hosted by ELIXIR Machine Learning Focus Group

24 September 2024 | 13:00 - 14:00 CEST

- **What are the DOME recommendations?**
- **What is the DOME registry?**
- **DOME use within ELIXIR - IDP Community**
- **DOME use beyond ELIXIR - GigaScience**

Please mute microphones during the presentations

Feel free to use "Chat" for questions, comments or discussions

Please use the "hand" function to indicate you would like to contribute directly
(The chair will invite you to speak)

This session will be recorded and made available on Youtube

We do not currently support Zoom Companion or other AI bots

This event follows the ELIXIR Code of Conduct.
If you have any concerns please refer to the Code of Conduct on the ELIXIR website

25 September
11-12.30 CEST | Online

RDM training annotation

Strategies for improved
curation in TeSS

Federico Bianchini
ELIXIR Norway

Alexander Botzki
ELIXIR Belgium

Registration is now open

ELIXIR Webinar

Hosted by the ELIXIR 3D Bioinfo Community

3DSig Session: Conformational Diversity

Xingyue Guan
Nanjing University
China

Dr. Lauren Porter
National Institute of Health (NIH)
USA

8th October 2024 | 17 hs CET | 16 hs UK time

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<https://elixir-europe.org/events>

A quick icebreaker

Go to <https://www.menti.com/>

Use Code: **6743 1033**

or

<https://www.menti.com/aleje65dc3dj>

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The DOME Recommendations

Fotis Psomopoulos
INAB|CERTH, ELIXIR-GR

www.elixir-europe.org

"Big Data" and AI is all the rage

IEEE Spectrum | 09

FEB 2022

Ng: Data-centric AI is the discipline of systematically engineering the data needed to successfully build an AI system. For an AI system, you have to implement some algorithm, say a neural network, in code and then train it on

at conferences and via publications. Today things are changing: networks, email, mobile devices, social media, shared storage, instant messaging, translation and video chat are letting scientists communicate with individuals and communities even when they are separated by time zones and large distances. And there is another major shift going on, which US computer scientist Jim Gray described in 2007 as "the fourth paradigm" for scientific exploration and discovery. He could see that the collection, analysis, and visualization of increasingly large amounts of data would change the very nature of science.

This is now happening. Over the past five years, the emergence of huge data sets and data-intensive science are fundamentally altering the way researchers work in virtually every scientific discipline. Biologists, chemists, physicists, astronomers, earth and social scientists are all benefiting from access to the tools and technologies that will integrate this "big data" into standard scientific methods and processes. Researchers are increasingly capable of collecting vast quantities of data through computer simulations, low-cost sensor networks and highly instrumented experiments, creating a "data deluge". Instead of just running computer simulations on HPC clusters and supercomputers, scientists now need a different type of computing resource to store and process these massive data sets. Researchers are exploring the use of an increasingly attractive, complementary source of computing power - the cloud. Particularly for the many scientists who may not have the time, access or expertise to use complex, in-house computing systems, cloud computing has opened another door to conducting data science on a large scale. With cloud computing, initial costs are minimized, the scaling of capacity is flexible, and access is more open and widespread. These characteristics look likely to generate

Science transformed

In science, people tend to associate big data with particle physics and astronomy. But these are just the start. Big data and cloud computing are touching many other fields and promise a widespread transformation in learning and discovery, as Tony Hey reveals

Riding the wave

How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data

Final report of the High Level Expert Group on Scientific Data
A submission to the European Commission
October 2010

nature International weekly journal of science

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BIG DATA

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- Features
- Commentary
- Books & Arts
- Essay
- Review
- Podcast Extra

EDITORIAL

ForbesBrandVoice Connecting marketers to the Forbes audience. [What is this?](#)

BUSINESS 4/16/2012 @ 12:00PM | 10,649 views

How Cloud and Big Data are Impacting the Human Genome - Touching 7 Billion Lives

by **Jacqueline Vanacek**, SAP

[Comment Now](#) [Follow Comments](#)

Mapping the "blueprint for building a person" is no small undertaking.

While the Human Genome Project formally began in 1990 and was completed in 2003, researchers continue to study the role of genes and proteins in building life.

The discovery of DNA is considered by some to be "the most important biological work of the last 100 years," and perhaps "the scientific frontier for the next 100."

Little did Watson and Crick know that when they first suggested the double helix structure for DNA,

A slight mutation in matched nucleotides can lead to chromosomal aberrations and unintentional genetic rearrangement. (Wikipedia)

BIG DATA // BIG DATA ANALYTICS

NEWS

5/10/2014 07:08 AM

UN Unveils Big Data Climate Change Challenge

United Nations hopes its big data climate contest will reveal new ways big data can alleviate problems caused by climate change.

The United Nations is hosting a global competition designed to spur the use of big data to tackle issues pertaining to climate change. The [Big Data Climate Challenge](#) (BDCC) seeks recently published or implemented projects that use big data and analytics to show the economic impact of changing climate patterns, and ways to manage their impact.

10 Big Data Pros To Follow On Twitter
(Click image for larger view and slideshow.)

Sponsor video, mouseover for sound

Machine learning is being used across many biological areas

CELL

- Biotherapeutic cell culture optimisation
- Cellular Image Analysis
- Cell type Annotation

GENOME

- ID gene coding regions
- Pharmacogenomics
- CRISPR Target sequence ID
- Methylation site ID
- Gene expression (microarrays)
- RNA structure

PROTEOME

- Protein Structure
- Protein-protein interactions
- Binding site ID

Corresponding growth of ML publications

The number of ML publications per year is based on Web of Science from 1996 onwards using the topic category for “machine learning” in combination with each of the following terms: “biolog”, “medicine”, “genom*”, “prote*”, “cell*”, “post translational”, “metabolic” and “clinical”.*

“~20% of publications did not apply any evaluation”¹

¹ Littmann, M. et al. **Validity of machine learning in biology and medicine increased through collaborations across fields of expertise.** *Nat. Mach. Intell.* 2, 18–24 (2020)

methods and 43% provided experimental proof, suggesting that such collaborations facilitate experimental and computational validation. On the flip side, 19% of all articles did not provide any evaluation; this number rose as high as 34% without computational co-authors (Fig. 2a).

No **independent** test sets

No **cross-validation**

No **statistical tests**

¹ Littmann, M. *et al.* Validity of machine learning in biology and medicine increased through collaborations across fields of expertise. *Nat. Mach. Intell.* **2**, 18–24 (2020)

THE ML FOCUS GROUP IN A NUTSHELL

Fotis Psomopoulos
(ELIXIR Greece)

Silvio Tosatto
(ELIXIR Italy)

Leyla Jael Castro
(ZB MED)

Goals

Standards for Machine Learning

Benchmarking of Machine Learning tools

Training for Machine Learning

Machine Learning
FAIR/reproducibility

Integration across ELIXIR Communities

Wide interest across all Nodes

- consistent participation >40 members , representing >10 Nodes
- Several outputs, incl. publications (*DOMÉ Recommendations, Synthetic data*), software services (*DOMÉ registry, DOMÉ Wizard*), and funded projects
- maintaining a connection to Industry (Owkin, Pistoia alliance) and international partners (NIH)

<https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/machine-learning>

DOME recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology published in **nature** **methods**

COMMENT | FOCUS

DOME: recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology

DOME is a set of community-wide recommendations for reporting supervised machine learning-based analyses applied to biological studies. Broad adoption of these recommendations will help improve machine learning assessment and reproducibility.

Ian Walsh, Dmytro Fishman, Dario Garcia-Gasulla, Tiina Titma, Gianluca Pollastri, ELIXIR Machine Learning Focus Group, Jennifer Harrow, Fotis E. Psomopoulos and Silvio C. E. Tosatto

With the steep decline in the cost of many high-throughput technologies, large amounts of biological data are being generated and made accessible to researchers. Machine learning (ML) has come into the spotlight as a very useful approach for understanding cellular, genomic, proteomic, post-translational, metabolic and drug discovery data, with the potential to result in ground-breaking medical applications¹. This is clearly reflected in the corresponding growth of ML publications (Fig. 1), reporting a wide range of modeling techniques in biology. While ideally ML methods should be validated experimentally, this happens only in a fraction of the publications². We believe that the time is right for the ML community to develop standards for reporting ML-based analyses to enable critical assessment³ and improve reproducibility^{4,5}.

Guidelines or recommendations on how to appropriately construct ML algorithms can help to ensure correct results and predictions^{6,7}. In biomedical research, communities have defined standard guidelines and best practices for scientific data management⁸ and reproducibility of computational tools^{9,10}. On the ML community side, there is demand for a cohesive and combined set of recommendations with respect to data, the optimization techniques, the final model, and evaluation protocols as a whole.

A recent comment highlighted the need for standards in ML¹¹, arguing for the adoption of on-submission checklists¹² as a first step toward improving publication standards. Through a community-driven consensus, we propose a list of minimal requirements asked as questions to ML implementers (Box 1) that, if followed, will help to assess the quality and reliability of reported methods more faithfully. We have focused on data, optimization, model and evaluation (DOME) as each component

of an ML implementation usually falls within one of these four topics. We do not propose new specific solutions, only recommendations (Table 1). A reporting checklist is also provided (Box 1). Our recommendations are made primarily for the case of supervised learning in biological applications in the absence of direct experimental validation, as this is the most common type of ML approach used. We do not discuss how ML can be used in clinical applications^{13,14}. It also remains to be determined whether the DOME recommendations can be extended to other fields of ML, like unsupervised, semisupervised and reinforcement learning.

Development of the recommendations
The recommendations outlined below were initially formulated through the ELIXIR Machine Learning Focus Group after the publication of a Comment calling for the establishment of standards for ML in biology¹¹. ELIXIR, initially established in 2014, is now a mature intergovernmental European infrastructure for biological data and represents over 220 research organizations in 22 countries across many aspects of bioinformatics¹⁵. Over 700 national experts participate in the development and operation of national services that contribute to data access, integration, training and analysis for the research community. Over 50 of these

Fig. 1 | Exponential increase of ML publications in biology. The number of ML publications per year is based on Web of Science from 1996 onwards using the topic category for "machine learning" in combination with each of the following terms: "biology", "medicine", "genom*", "prote*", "cell*", "post translational", "metabolic" and "clinical".

1122

NATURE METHODS | VOL 18 | OCTOBER 2021 | 1122-1144 | www.nature.com/naturemethods

Data Optimisation Model Evaluation

- CELL**
 - Biotherapeutic cell culture optimisation
 - Cellular Image Analysis
 - Cell type Annotation
- GENOME**
 - ID gene coding regions
 - Pharmacogenomics
 - CRISPR Target sequence ID
 - Methylation side ID
 - Gene expression (microarrays)
 - RNA structure
- PROTEOME**
 - Protein Structure
 - Protein-protein interactions
 - Binding site ID
- PTMS/METABOLISM**
 - Protein small molecule interaction
 - PTM protein amino acid site ID
 - Metabolic pathways

Set of recommendations for supervised learning with aim to improve standards

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01205-4>

20k Accesses, 112 Citations, 83 Altmetric (Sep 2024)

FAIRsharing.org standard (Record ID: 1180)
standards, databases, policies

D_{ata}

- Provenance
- Data splits
- Redundancy between data splits
- Availability of data

O_{ptimisation}

- Algorithm
- Meta-predictions
- Data encoding
- Parameters
- Features
- Fitting
- Availability of configuration

M_{odel}

- Interpretability
- Execution time
- Availability of software

E_{valuation}

- Evaluation method
- Performance measures
- Comparison
- Confidence
- Availability of evaluation

Data Optimisation Model Evaluation

- Provenance
- Data splits
- Redundancy
- Availability

Provenance	<i>Protein Data Bank (PDB). X-ray structures missing residues. $N_{pos} = 339,603$ residues. $N_{neg} = 6,168,717$ residues. Previously used in (Walsh et al., Bioinformatics 2015) as an independent benchmark set.</i>
Dataset splits	<i>training set: N/A $N_{pos,test} = 339,603$ residues. $N_{neg,test} = 6,168,717$ residues. No validation set. 5.22% positives on the test set.</i>
Redundancy between data splits	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Availability of data	<i>Yes, URL: http://protein.bio.unipd.it/mobidblite/. Free use license.</i>

Example paper used:

Marco Necci, et al, "MobiDB-lite: fast and highly specific consensus prediction of intrinsic disorder in proteins", Bioinformatics, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btx015>

Data Optimisation Model Evaluation

- Algorithm
- Meta-predictions
- Data encoding
- Parameters
- Features
- Fitting
- Availability

Algorithm	<i>Majority-based consensus classification based on 8 primary ML methods and post-processing.</i>
Meta-predictions	<i>Yes, predictor output is a binary prediction computed from the consensus of other methods; Independence of training sets of other methods with test set of meta-predictor was not tested since datasets from other methods were not available.</i>
Data encoding	<i>Label-wise average of 8 binary predictions.</i>
Parameters	<i>$p = 3$ (Consensus score threshold, expansion-erosion window, length threshold). No optimization.</i>
Features	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Fitting	<i>Single input ML methods are used with default parameters. Optimization is a simple majority.</i>
Regularization	<i>No.</i>
Availability of configuration	<i>Not applicable.</i>

Data Optimisation **Model** Evaluation

Interpretability	<i>Transparent, in so far as meta-prediction is concerned. Consensus and post processing over other methods predictions (which are mostly balck boxes). No attempt was made to make the meta-prediction a black box.</i>
Output	<i>Classification, i.e. residues thought to be disordered.</i>
Execution time	<i>ca. 1 second per representative on a desktop PC.</i>
Availability of software	<i>Yes, URL: http://protein.bio.unipd.it/mobidblite/. Bespoke license free for academic use.</i>

- Interpretability
- Execution time
- Software Availability

Example paper used:

Marco Necci, et al, "MobiDB-lite: fast and highly specific consensus prediction of intrinsic disorder in proteins", *Bioinformatics*, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btx015>

Data Optimisation Model Evaluation

Evaluation method	<i>Independent dataset</i>
Performance measures	<i>Balanced Accuracy, Precision, Sensitivity, Specificity, F1, MCC.</i>
Comparison	<i>DisEmbl-465, DisEmbl-HL, ESpritz Disprot, ESpritz NMR, ESpritz Xray, Globplot, IUPred long, IUPred short, VSL2b. Chosen methods are the methods from which the meta prediction is obtained.</i>
Confidence	<i>Not calculated.</i>
Availability of evaluation	<i>No.</i>

- Evaluation
- Performance
- Comparison
- Confidence Availability

Example paper used:

Marco Necci, et al, "MobiDB-lite: fast and highly specific consensus prediction of intrinsic disorder in proteins", *Bioinformatics*, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btx015>

Take home message and road ahead

There is a need for **AI standards** in Life Sciences, and DOME is one of the established solutions.

The DOME standard is an actionable outcome, usable by the wider scientific community, including:

- Researchers
- Publishers
- Funders
- Policy makers

Moving ahead

we plan to *engage with all stakeholders*, and promote *adoption* and *growth* of the standard itself (by expanding to new methods and domains)

Acknowledgements

The ELIXIR Machine Learning Focus Group Community

MACHINE LEARNING
FOCUS GROUP

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DI PADOVA

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What is the DOME registry?

Silvio Tosatto

University of Padova & ELIXIR Italy

From the DOME recommendations to the DOME registry

DOME Registry: Implementing community-wide recommendations for reporting supervised machine learning in biology

Omar Abdelghani Attafi^{1,*}, Damiano Clementel^{1,*}, Konstantinos Kyritsis², Emidio Capriotti³, Gavin Farrell⁴, Styliani-Christina Fragkouli^{2,5}, Leyla Jael Castro⁶, András Hatos^{7,8,9,10}, Tom Lenaerts^{11,12,13}, Stanislav Mazurenko^{14,15}, Soroush Mozaffari¹, Franco Pradelli¹, Patrick Ruch^{16,17}, Castrense Savojardo³, Paola Turina³, Federico Zambelli^{18,19}, Damiano Piovesan¹, Alexander Miguel Monzon²⁰, Fotis Psomopoulos^{2,7}, Silvio C.E. Tosatto^{1,21*}

DOME
recommendations

Paper

Curators

DOME registry

Idea: develop an online platform to provide a curated set of annotations for machine learning papers fulfilling the DOME Recommendations.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.07721>

DOME Registry

A database of annotations for published papers describing machine learning methods in biology.

Machine learning (ML) methods have been widely used in biology for the last few decades. The description of ML methods in publications benefits from the standardization of terminology and reporting of technical details. To this end, the DOME recommendations ([Walsh et al, Nature Methods 2021](#)) provide an easy to follow template.

The DOME registry provides a curated set of annotations for ML papers following the DOME recommendations.

Browse

82

 Users

193

 Entries

27

 In progress

Users

82

Private annotations

27

Public annotations

193

Total annotations

221

DOME Registry - Annotations

DOME Score

Section	Score
Dataset	4 / 4 (100%)
Optimization	7 / 8 (88%)
Model	4 / 4 (100%)
Evaluation	5 / 5 (100%)
Total	20 / 21 (95%)

The DOME score is compute as the number of valid fields, divided by the total number of fields

Invalid field

Is the algorithm a meta-predictor?

No

Does the model use data from other machine-learning algorithms as input (i.e. it is a meta-predictor)?

If it is a meta-predictor, which machine-learning methods constitute the whole?

If it is a meta-predictor, is it completely clear that training data of initial predictors and meta-predictor is independent of test data for the meta-predictor?

DOME Data Stewardship Wizard

Create Project

From Project Template Custom

Name

Knowledge Model

DOME 0.5.0
DOME Knowledge Model

newProject

Questionnaire Metrics Preview Documents Settings

View

Chapters	
I. Instructions	✓
II. Curator information	2
III. Publication	6
IV. Data	4
V. Optimization	8
VI. Model	4
VII. Evaluation	5

II. Curator information

Please fill up the following information

II.1 Email

Please type the email related to your orcid account

II.2 ORCID ID

16-digit ORCID ID (format XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX)

<https://dome.dsw.elixir-europe.org/wizard/>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QNPzQrIeTkk>

APICURON Databases Curators Docs Help About Silvio Tosatto

APICURON

The database to credit and acknowledge the work of biocurators.

APICURON collects and aggregates biocuration events from third party resources and generates **achievements** and **leaderboards** !

If you are a biocurator and want to appear here ask your database manager to contact us. [Read more](#)

Search Biocurators

DOME Dome Registry

[View Details](#)

The DOME registry allows users to contribute annotations. These submitted annotations will be subject to a rigorous manual review process, culminating in eventual publication. Published annotations will be accessible to the public but rendered immutable. Conversely, unpublished annotations will remain subject to...

Last Submission Date: 23-06-2024 UTC

APICURON Databases Curators Docs Help About Login

DOME

Dome Registry

The DOME registry allows users to contribute annotations. These submitted annotations will be subject to a rigorous manual review process, culminating in eventual publication. Published annotations will be accessible to the public but rendered immutable. Conversely, unpublished annotations will remain subject to user-driven viewing, editing, and deletion.

Weekly Leaderboard **Total Leaderboard**

Ranking	Curator	Medals	Badges	Generation Contributions	Invalidation Contributions	Revision Contributions	Total Score	Last Contribution Date
1	Styliani Christina Fragkouli	2	2	15	0	0	150	01-09-2022
2	Stanislav Mazurenko	2	2	15	0	0	150	01-09-2022
3	Franco Pradelli	1	2	12	0	0	120	01-09-2022
4	András Hatos	1	2	11	0	0	110	01-09-2022
5	MARIA PAOLA TURINA	1	2	10	0	0	100	20-05-2024
6	Gavin Farrell	0	2	10	0	0	100	23-06-2024

Total Contributors: **6** < 1 >

APICURON

<https://apicuron.org/>

Acknowledgements

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